

Reading Strategies Intervention to Enhance Reading Comprehension of the Students of Law

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Abstract- Reading is considered one of the most important skills in the process of second language learning. It is one of the important language skills for academic success. Law students, in Indian law schools, have to go through various legislative texts, juridical writings and academic legal writing texts in their course of study. Comprehending the specific lexicon used in these texts, especially, in court Judgments, in Acts, contracts, etc. becomes difficult for beginners. This results in an inaccurate and inappropriate comprehension of the overall document. Thus it becomes essential for the legal language teacher to improve and enhance the reading ability of the students and to prepare them for the complicated legal industry. Developing comprehension through reading strategies is one solution for such a challenge. Thus the paper aims to devise a few essential reading strategies, that a language teacher can use in his/her class to develop the comprehension of the budding lawyers. The study is the result of the action research conducted on the first-semester students of the Department of Law, enrolled in the BALLB Five-year integrated program at AMU, and her own experience of teaching legal language over there.

Index Terms- legal language, reading, comprehension, strategies, action research.

I. INTRODUCTION

The pedagogical limitations and methodical application placed on ESL learners provide a significant problem for English teachers when it comes to measuring reading proficiency. Having good reading comprehension helps students make sense of the material by using both the texts and their past learning resources to grasp its intricacies. This research is devoted to finding out the benefits and effectiveness of reading strategies in student's reading comprehension, thus in this way devising a few essential reading strategies for struggling legal language teachers. The study is the result of the research conducted on the first semester students of the department of law, enrolled in the BALLB Five-year integrated programme at AMU, and her own experience of teaching legal language over there

II. LITERATURE REVIEW:

Reading, out of the four language skills is long believed as the most important skill. In 1917 Thorndike[1] talked about the difference between simply saying the words to oneself while reading, and on the other hand understanding the material read as a problem-solving process. During that time reading was viewed as thinking, which involves a whole complex of skills and abilities. According to Thorndike (1917), reading a paragraph and thinking consisted of similar organization and analysis. It includes learning, recall, imagination, organization, analysis, selection, evaluation, inferencing, problem-solving, judgment and so on. Hildreth[2] (1958:72) while describing the reading process said "Reading requires inferences, weighing the relative importance of ideas and meanings, and seeing the relationship among them; it is a process of forming tentative judgments, then verifying and checking guesses. To solve the problems in a passage the reader must be continuously in an alert, anticipatory frame of mind, suspending judgment, correcting and confirming his guesses as he goes along." More recently researchers like Rumelhart[3] (1977) agreed that reading comprehension involves both background knowledge of the reader, and what information and meaning he can able to extract from the given reading text, and came up with the "Interactive Model of Reading" in comparison, to Goodman's [4] (1967) "Top-Down Model of Reading" and Gough's[5] (1972) "Bottom-up Model of Reading". In agreement with this view, Carpenter[6] (2002:30) said "Reading is a process where background knowledge and language knowledge interact and where the reader actively constructs meaning". McDonough and Shaw[7] (1993:101) proved "As a skill, reading is one of the most important".

III. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM:

IV. To be an accomplished lawyer or legal professional, in-depth, conceptual knowledge, updated information, excellent skill and expertise are required, which can be achieved by reading extensively in various areas of law. One should be an avid and constant reader to acquire competency right from being a law student to a law professional. The various kinds of material law students are required to read in their student and professional life are legal texts, case laws, court judgments, Acts, scholarly articles, legal commentary, newspapers etc. According to Christensen's[8] (2007) research, "Legal Reading and Success in Law School: An Empirical Study," students who can accurately and effectively read court rulings perform better academically than those who are less adept at it.

Students, who are enrolled in the Five Years Integrated BALLB programme, in the Faculty of Law, Aligarh Muslim University, are those students, who have cracked the competition to get admission over there. Thus, one can have a preconceived assumption that such students might be excellent in the English language. This misapprehension is called a "skills deployment assumption" (Stratman, 1990)[9]. However, the majority of law students find reading and comprehending legal materials to be a difficult task. One probable reason behind this is the heterogeneity. Some students are from a non-English background and in AMU the medium of instruction is English, because most of the sound material, in law discipline, is available in the English language as it is the only lingua franca available. This is one area of difficulty due to which students face difficulty in comprehending whatever they read.

The second and most noteworthy reason is the complex linguistic nature of the language of Law itself. Language of law, also called legalese, because of its unusual framework, has always been problematic not only to the legal fraternity but for a lay person too. This complexity and obscurity of legal language result in a greater incomprehensibility than a thorough comprehension of the legal texts. Badger[10] (2003, p.251) contented that "law reports have unusual vocabulary and complex syntax", Christensen[8] (2007) supported the argument by describing her reading of law judgment as "confusing, mystifying and unfamiliar". Tiersma[11] (1999:5), describes legal language as "ponderous, arcane and obscure" (p.5). The various peculiar and unusual features of legal language which lead to its complexity and obscurity are Latin and French words, circumlocution, long and complex sentences, nominalization, archaic words, use of binomials and trinomials, negative constructions, anachronism, wordiness etc. Although, in other disciplines, drafters have shifted to the use of modern English, legal drafters have decided to retain the old tradition. Possible reasons may be the conservatism of the profession and legal language is recognised as the product of its history. Thus, due to these mystifying and perplexing features, legal language is treated as "regal, formal, unintelligible and impenetrable" by ordinary minds (Mellinkoff[12] 1963 in Tiersma, 1999; Phillips, 1987[13]; Phillips, 2003[14]). These reasons result in the incomprehensibility of any of the legal text. Owing to this problem, a few fruitful reading strategies are devised for the language instructor to improve, enhance and strengthen the reading comprehension skills of the law students. Having the awareness of reading strategies is very beneficial for all kinds of readers as it helps them to "set a purpose for reading, self-question, search for important information, make inferences, summarise and monitor the developing meaning" (Dewitz, 1997, p.228).[15]

IV. READING COMPREHENSION:

"Comprehension is the process of simultaneously extracting and constructing meaning through interaction and involvement with written language" (RAND Reading Study Group, 2001, p. 11)[16]. Undoubtedly it can be called the final product or result of the process of reading. Reading without the achievement of any comprehension is a useless activity. According to Grabe[17] (2009:14), "reading is centrally a comprehending process". Snow[18] (2002:11) defines reading comprehension as "the process of simultaneously extracting and constructing meaning through interaction and involvement with written language." As the discussion of the definition of reading itself, readers extract information from the printed texts to construct the meaning of the texts. The task of a responsible reader is to extract accurately the intended meaning of the written text. Reading for the sake of reading and reading for comprehension are two different objectives of any reader. Reading is an activity which involves recognition of the printed words, pronouncing them correctly and guessing their meaning based on the context. Whereas comprehension is the understanding of the meaning of text depending upon the need and purpose of the reader, his level of understanding and the strategies he has used in inferring that meaning. In the words of Harrison[19] (2004:51) comprehension is "the process of getting meaning of a communication, as a personal letter, speech, sign language; the knowledge or understanding that is the result of such a process." Similarly, according to Ahmadi [20](2013:238) defines reading comprehension as "the ability of readers to understand the surface and the hidden meanings of the text using meta-cognitive reading strategies". Thus if reading is a "form" then comprehension is a "result".

V. NEED OF READING COMPREHENSION STRATEGIES:

There is an extensive amount of research available proving the effective role of reading comprehension strategies in the notable improvement of reading comprehension. Ultimately "The goal of all readers should be to understand what they

read” (Teele, 2004, p. 92)[21]. An intelligent and conscious reader is one who is immensely involved with his reading material and very well aware of the selection of processes to comprehend that material. But comprehension is not an easy task, for however there are several factors which may affect intelligent comprehension. According to Pressley [22](2000) word-level skills, readers' Schema and the use of appropriate comprehension strategies, are the elements that affect comprehension. Understanding strategies are seen as conscious, controllable, and observable processes. As a result, strategy teaching might be used as a method to enhance comprehension.

Law students, in particular, face great difficulty in comprehending legal texts, especially, contracts, court judgments, case laws, various acts of the parliament etc. because of its complicated and antiquated sentence structure and specific jargon. In order to comprehend such texts not only the knowledge of the lexicon or text structure knowledge is sufficient but background knowledge and knowledge of culture is also required. They should bring in “real-world knowledge” to comprehend such complicated and unique texts (Deegan, 1995)[23]. Moreover, knowledge of reading strategies can go a long way beyond helping these novice legal readers comprehend legal texts along with all their intricacies. Dewitz, (1997, p.228)[24] suggested that reading strategies are very beneficial for readers as they “set a purpose for reading, self-question, search for important information, make inferences, summarize and monitor the developing meaning”. Thus, it becomes the duty of the language instructor to not only teach but also make the students aware of the different reading strategies, because “when readers did not use appropriate reading strategies, they had problems with guessing the meaning of words, relied on word by word translation, often made inaccurate guesses and could not retain the meaning of what they read...”. (Hosenfeld, 1976)[25]. Taking into account some of these concerns, the study aims at devising a few reading strategies which can prove very beneficial for law scholars and which can make them proficient and independent readers.

VI. READING COMPREHENSION STRATEGIES:

Reading strategies may be defined as “problem-solving techniques” (Barnett 1988b:150)[26] or “ways” (Urquhart and Weir 1998:95)[27] for getting out of those problems that occur during reading. According to Barnett (1988:150), [26] “reading strategies are the mental operations involved when readers approach a text effectively and make sense of what they read”. These are cognitive processes that help “to enhance reading comprehension failures” (Singhal, 2001, p. 2) [28] According to Harris and Graham., “A strategy is a special form of procedural knowledge that is intentionally purposefully and effortfully applied to a given task or situation for which one’s typical or automatic pattern of thought or behaviour is perceived as inadequate or non-optimal” (Harris, Alexander and S. Graham, 2008, p. 89) [29]. Thus readers employ reading strategies as control mechanisms that give them control over the material they receive and understand. Based on the above definitions, it can be safely concluded that reading comprehension strategies are those tools or resources chosen by readers which help them to comprehend the text exactly, tackle the textual problems, and dig out the hidden meaning. Some reading strategies which are used in this research are:

a) Identifying: As a first step in the process of reading or before coming to the actual reading of the text, the language instructor should ask the students to set a purpose for their reading. It is one of the marks of a good reader. They should know whether they are reading for the information, for pleasure or meaning. In the law classroom, the instructor may ask the students to read the text like a lawyer or a judge so that they can set the purpose of reading accordingly and it will also give them practice in using problematic and rhetorical strategies.

b) Predicting: This strategy helps the students to identify the purpose of their reading. According to (Block & Israel, 2005) proficient readers draw on their previous experiences and knowledge to envisage and come up with new concepts when they read. Through this strategy, students get a chance to interact with the text and to compare between their prediction and the actual result of the text. This activity develops interest in reading and finally improves understanding of the text. Predicting and guessing difficult words, using headings, subheadings, keywords, pictures and titles for prediction are some of the effective activities for prediction.

c) Visualizing: Visualisation is the image of some object form in the mind. As a reading strategy, it makes the students form an image of their reading material. The reader retains this image in their mind as a picture of how they understand the text. (National Reading Panel, 2000). Arranging textual information graphically strengthens both the verbal and visual memory of the reader. In law discipline, as the students read the facts in the case laws, legal problems or illustrations, the teacher can ask the students to visualise those facts along with the characters and objects involved. In personal law problems, students can even draw a tree diagram chart, as they read, to better understand the relationships among characters involved. They can even arrange their notes in a timeline or in flowchart format to remember and understand better. This strategy is very beneficial as it can create the whole image of a legal problem in the mind of the readers, hence an aid to comprehension.

d) Forming Connections: This strategy is also very helpful in reading. It goes along with visualization. As a use of this strategy, the teacher can ask the students to connect the material or content of their reading to their own experience, to the other lexical and graphic organizers in the text or to the previously decided case having the same facts (*stare decisis*). When the readers know that they have to make connections on various levels of their reading content, as they read, their reading definitely will become more vigilant, more careful, and hence more meaningful.

e) Skimming: Skimming is also a good while-reading strategy. Students can give one quick reading to the entire text just to understand the overall gist of the text. Through this strategy they can come to know, the overall subject of the text, the main idea of the text and the important details given. The strategy helps the students to decide on a further plan or strategy for their reading.

f) Scanning: Scanning is also a beneficial while-reading activity. The teacher may ask the students to give one quick reading of the text and gather the specific or required information. Students can scan the reading text and search for the information like name of the parties, date and time of the event, material and general facts, names of the other people involved in the case, like witness (es) etc. This strategy helps the students to gather the relevant information from the text quickly. If the students are conscious of their reading, they can make their reading meaningful.

g) Inferencing: Inferencing is “to make assumptions and logical deductions from concrete ideas” (Cuperman, 2014:50)[30]. It is to make intelligent guesses. when the information is not stated directly in the text, students can make use of this strategy to infer such information. It is to understand those implied meanings which are not stated on the face of the text, but which are to be understood by reading between the lines. Students can make use of “syntactic, logical and cultural clues to discover the meaning of these unknown elements” (Grellet, 2010) [31]. The students of law can make use of this strategy specially to understand the terms of any contract, policy, opinion of judges etc. Inferencing is not a certainty but a near possibility. Students can be taught how to conclude using titles from the text, graphs, images, times, and associated language.

h) Monitoring: Monitoring is the control of reading. In general, it is “the ability to know what has been done right or wrong and to integrate new information with prior existing knowledge” (Yang, 2002:19)[32]. Hogan (2011:8)[33] commented that monitoring “involves the capacity to reflect on one’s comprehension and includes the ability to detect inconsistencies within a text”. In the legal language classroom, the teacher may ask the students to monitor their style of reading, and the type of strategies they are using, and then to check logically whether the strategies they are using are helping them in acquiring the text accurately or not. The objective of monitoring is “to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of a project... It facilitates keeping the work on track...it is an invaluable tool for better controlling while reading” (Ahmadi, 2013:237,238) [20]. In a law classroom teacher can ask the students to differentiate between clauses, sub-clauses, sections and sub-sections, while reading the Acts, to question the author while reading judgments, case reports, or judicial opinions, to find out the errors in their comprehension while reading the law problems, to facilitate their reading comprehension skill.

i) Evaluation: In the words of Ahmadi et al. (2013:238) [20] evaluation means “appraising the conclusion and regulatory processes of an individual’s learning”. After reading the given text, the teacher can aware the students about the mistakes they have committed in their entire reading process, the problems they have come across, the challenging areas and so on, to develop their evaluation skills and to make them conscious of their reading. Teachers should appreciate the student’s comprehension of the text and should guide them towards the selection of appropriate strategies in the situation of incomprehensibility.

j) Questioning: This strategy can be used at any point in the entire process of reading. Readers must ask themselves questions as part of the questioning process to create meaning, deepen comprehension, identify solutions, resolve issues, locate information, and uncover new information. Teachers should ask the students to keep on asking questions to themselves regarding their comprehension, throughout the reading process. Students may get involved in rereading the same text to find out the probable answer to their questions, and finding the clues and graphic hints to their legal problems Students are asked to return to the text to find the answer to questions. Students are trained to ask questions and assess whether they are literal, figurative, or predicated on prior information. Text parts are combined and reading comprehension is subsequently improved by employing the student-generated questioning strategy.

VII. Question of Action Research:

This research paper aims to devise certain effective reading strategies to improve the reading comprehension of the students of law. According to the teacher researcher, students will suffer academically and professionally as well, if they do not have an appropriate knowledge in reading skills. By teaching reading comprehension techniques, the

researcher intends to raise her students' reading awareness and provide them with a more fulfilling reading experience. The research question is, "whether reading comprehension strategies can improve the reading comprehension skills of law students or not?" The study has assessed the improvement in students' reading comprehension skills after giving them training on reading comprehension strategies.

VIII. Method

The methodology adopted for this research is the "Action research Model" as this model is problem-solving and allows collaboration of both researcher and participant. It is a student-centered model and its method is to first devise what needs to change, and second, give a proper procedure for that change. According to Brown and Dowling (2001) [34], "action research is a term which is applied to projects in which practitioners seek to effect transformation in their practices...". The steps of action research are: "planning, acting, observing, reflecting" (McNiff, 1988: 22)[35]. Research findings prove that students' comprehension is enhanced when they are aware of the reading comprehension strategy they are employing and how it contributes to the text's meaning.

IX. Data Collection and Research Procedure:

In this research paper, ten strategies are used, namely, Identifying, Predicting, Visualising, Forming connections, Skimming, Scanning, Inferencing, Monitoring, Evaluation and Questioning. The students were first made aware of the strategies, and then they were asked to make use of those strategies whenever they indulged in the reading activity, according to their reading needs. This training went on for three weeks. In the survey related to the students' awareness regarding the strategies, it was found that nearly 70% of the students were not aware of the reading strategies. The teacher-researcher then first gave a detailed presentation of all the strategies, followed by guided and finally independent practice by the students. During the phase of independent reading, the teacher researcher used the Meta comprehension Strategy Index (MSI) to evaluate if any change occurred in the comprehension behaviour of the students or not. Reading material like law problems, court judgments, contract law, contract documents, policy documents, service agreement forms etc. were used in this experiment.

X. Result & conclusion

The outcome of the study suggests that a well-designed reading strategy curriculum and the students' knowledge of the various reading strategies as well as their potential to select the best suitable strategy according to their reading needs, plays a significant role in improving their comprehension of what they read. Both my own experience and the findings of the reading awareness score indicated that, at the beginning of the research, students knew very little about reading strategies. After the presentation on the reading comprehension strategies, and their actual implementation, the comprehension level of the students was improved greatly. The research is very beneficial for the English language instructor because it devises their reading strategies as well as also gives a plan on how to incorporate the strategies into the teaching-learning methodology. The study is beneficial to the students as well; as they have enhanced their comprehension of reading and have gained a better grasp of the strategies. Thus in this way, the study has devised a few essential reading strategies for legal language instructors as well as for law students along with benefits.

REFERENCES:

1. Thorndike, E.L. (1917). Reading as Reasoning: A Study of Mistakes in Paragraph Reading. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 8 (pp.323-332).
2. Hildreth, Gertrude. (1958). *Teaching Reading*. New York: Holt, Rinehart and Winston Inc.
3. Rumelhart, D. (1977). Towards an Interactive Model of Reading. In S. Dornic (ed.), *Attention and Performance IV* (pp. 573-603). New York: Academic Press.
4. Goodman, K. (1967). Reading: A psycholinguistic Guessing Game. *Journal of the Reading Specialist*, 6, 126-135.
5. Gough (1972). One Second of Reading. In J.K. Kavanagh and I.G. Mattingly (eds.), *Language by Ear and by Eye*. Cambridge:Mass., MIT Press.
6. Carpenter, C. (2002). *Modern World History: An L2 reading Curriculum for the Japanese Context*. Paper Presented at the Department of Applied Linguistics and ESL. Georgia State University.
7. Mc Donough, J. and Shaw, C. (1993). *Materials and Methods in ELT*. Oxford: OUP.
8. Christensen, L. (2007). Legal reading and success in law school: an empirical study. *30 Seattle University Law Review* 603.
9. Stratman, J.F. (1990). The emergence of legal composition as a field of inquiry: evaluating the prospects. *Review of Educational Research* 60,153-235
10. Badger, R. (2003). Legal & general: towards a genre analysis of newspaper law reports. *English for Specific Purposes* 22 (2003) 249-263
11. Tiersma, P. M. (1999). *Legal Language*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press. York: Routledge.

12. Mellinkoff, D. (1963). *The language of the law*. In P. M. Tiersma. (1999). *Legal Language*. Chicago: The University of Chicago Press.
13. Phillips, A. (1987). *The Lawyer and Society*. Glasgow: Ardmoray Publishing.
14. Phillips, A. (2003). *Lawyer's Language: How and why legal language is different*. New Publications.
15. Dewitz, P. (1997). *Legal education: a problem of learning from text*. In L. Christensen (2007). *Legal reading and success in law school: an empirical study*. 30 *Seattle University Law Review* 603.
16. RAND Reading Study Group (2001). *Reading for understanding: Toward an R&D program in reading comprehension*. Tech. rep. RAND
17. Grabe, W. (2009). *Reading in a Foreign Language: Moving from theory to practice*. New York: Cambridge University Press
18. Snow, C. (2002). *Reading for Understanding: Toward a Research and Developmental Program in Reading Comprehension*. California: RAND Corporation.
19. Harrison, C. 2004. *Understanding Reading Development*. London: SAGE Publication.
20. Ahmadi, M. R., Ismail, H. N., and Abdullah, M. K. K. (2013). *The importance of metacognitive reading strategy awareness in reading comprehension*. *English Language Teaching*. v. 6 (10), pp. 235-244.
21. Teele, S. (2004). *Overcoming barricades to reading a multiple intelligences approach*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Corwin Press
22. Pressley, M. (2000). 'What should comprehension instruction be the instruction of?' In: *Handbook of Reading Research*. Ed. by M. Kamil et al. Vol. 3. Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum, pp. 545–561.
23. Deegan, D.H. (1995). *Exploring individual differences among novices reading in a specific domain: the case of Law*. 30 *Reading Research Quarterly* 154,157
24. Dewitz, P. (1997). *Legal education: a problem of learning from text*. In L. Christensen (2007). *Legal reading and success in law school: an empirical study*. 30 *Seattle University Law Review* 603.
25. Hosenfeld, C. (1976) *Discovering our students' strategies*. *Foreign Language Annals*, 9, 117-130.
26. Barnett, M.A. (1988b). *Reading through Context: How Real and Perceived Strategy Use Affects L2 Comprehension*. *Modern Language Journal*, 72 (pp. 150-159).
27. Urquhart, A.H., and Weir C.J. (1998). *Reading in a Second Language: Process, Product and Practice*. London: Longman. Pearson Education Ltd.
28. Singhal, M. (2001). 'Reading proficiency, reading strategies, metacognitive awareness and L2 readers'. In: *The Reading Matrix* 1, pp. 1–23.
29. Harris, K., P. Alexander and S. Graham (2008). 'Michael Pressley's Contributions to the History and Future of Strategies Research'. In: *Educational Psychologist* 43.2, pp. 86–96.
30. Cuperman, R. C. (2014). *Anticipation and prediction: something has happened inside the reader*. Library Media Connection
31. Grellet, F. (2010). *Developing Reading Skills: A Practical Guide to Reading Comprehension Exercises*. United Kingdom: Cambridge University Press.
32. Yang, Y. (2002). *Reassessing readers' comprehension monitoring*. *Reading in a Foreign Language*. v.14 (1), pp. 18-42.
33. Hogan, T. P., Bridges, M. S., Justice, L. M. and Cain, K. (2011). *Increasing higher reading skills to improve reading comprehension*. *Focus on Exceptional Children*. v. 44 (3), pp. 1-20.
34. Brown, A., & Dowling, P. (2001). *Doing research/reading research: A mode of interrogation for teaching*. London, England: Routledge Falmer
35. McNiff, J. (1988). *Action research: principles and practice*. London, England: Routledge.